

Has climate change driven the Galapagos Damsel fish, *Azurina eupalama*, to extinction?

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Abstract

The endemic Galapagos Damsel fish, *Azurina eupalama*, has not been seen since the historically large El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) of 1982/3. Many observers and expeditions have attempted to find the species in the more than 4 decades since, but without success. Prior to 1982, the species had been regularly observed and numerous specimens were collected by almost all historical collecting expeditions conducted since the species was discovered in 1898. During ENSO events, the cessation of cold upwelling and high plankton productivity typical of normal years results in sustained periods of exceptionally warm water, reducing populations of cool-water fishes and severely affecting many other marine and terrestrial organisms. The endemic Galapagos Damsel fish was an obligate planktivore, limited to the exposed shallow shorelines of the islands of the Galapagos (Ecuador), and adapted to cooler sea-surface temperatures, making the species especially vulnerable to extinction due to climate change and concomitant oceanographic perturbations. The Galapagos Damsel fish, presently classified by the IUCN Red List as critically endangered/possibly extinct, should now be considered likely extinct. Future searches by sampling environmental DNA from Galapagos waters may be able to further confirm this tragic outcome of human-induced global climate change on this fragile and uniquely iconic World Heritage Site.

Key words: Ecuador, El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO), tropical eastern Pacific, marine biology, ichthyology, shorefishes, coral-reef fishes, archipelago, endemism, biogeography, World Heritage Site.

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The ENSO effect on Galapagos

Global climate change and its concomitant oceanographic effects, in particular more frequent and more intense El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) events, has had a profound influence on marine ecosystems in the tropical Eastern Pacific (TEP) region (Cai et al. 2020). The primary mediator is markedly higher water temperatures occurring more frequently, extending deeper, and for longer durations than the ecosystem has experienced for many hundreds, perhaps thousands, of years (Fig. 1). The worldwide oceanographic effects are altered current regimes, atypical temperature-depth profiles, and pronounced fluctuations in a host of critical factors, including oxygenation, pH, salinity, turbidity, turbulence, elemental nutrients, and primary productivity (Cai et al. 2021).

The Galapagos Islands of Ecuador are especially sensitive to ENSO events. The archipelago is situated at the epicenter of the major oceanographic perturbations in the TEP during the ENSO, i.e. an isolated island group far from the influence of the continent, on the equator, and at the intersection of major warm and cold currents, providing a unique set of features underlying the extraordinary diversity of both marine and terrestrial life. The marine ecosystem, in particular, is highly dependent, and adapted to, seasonal cycles of upwelling and the nutrients and productivity associated with the rise of deeper cool waters (Schaeffer et al. 2008).

During the ENSO, warm water with low productivity extends wider and deeper around the islands and persists longer (Fig. 2), resulting in coral bleaching and acidification and sharp declines in phytoplankton productivity and zooplankton densities. This results in marked reductions in the supply of food for planktivores, especially shoreline and reef-associated fishes who cannot move between islands or move into deeper waters.

The 1982/3 ENSO was the largest recorded ENSO at the time and resulted in profound and long-lasting changes in the marine environment (Fig. 1) (Glynn 1990). Corals suffered extreme bleaching mortality and have not recovered – well developed coral colonies and reefs disappeared and reef-framework structures more than 1,000 years old were completely bioeroded in less than a decade after the massive ENSO (Glynn 1994, 2001). Many locations worldwide were documented to have coral and reefs decimated (Hoegh-Guldberg et al. 2007), but the Galapagos is exceptional in that it represents the only known case where complete elimination of the reef framework occurred following coral mortality (Glynn et al. 2009). Several intense ENSOs followed after 1983, including a sharp and well documented ENSO of 1997/8 that resulted in severe effects on the Galapagos fauna and flora (Figs. 1 & 2) (Podesta & Glynn 2001).

Fig. 1. The multivariate El Niño/Southern Oscillation Index (MEI), integrating sea-level pressure (P), zonal (U) and meridional (V) components of the surface wind, sea surface temperature (S), surface air temperature (A), and total cloudiness fraction of the sky (C) of the tropical Pacific Ocean (positive departure (red) is a measure of the intensity of the ENSO). From the International Comprehensive Ocean-Atmosphere Data Set of the NOAA Physical Sciences Laboratory, following Wolter & Timlin (1998).

Fig. 2. Satellite images of chlorophyll-a concentrations, reflecting primary productivity, from during the 1998/9 ENSO (left) and the return of the normal pattern of upwelling of cooler water on the west side of the archipelago (right). The false color images document phytoplankton concentrations for 10 May 1998 (left) and after the end of the ENSO on 25 May 1998 (right). High concentrations are shown in red and low concentrations in blue, with areas occluded by clouds in white and a relief image of the Galapagos islands superimposed. Images courtesy NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center, The SeaWiFS Project and GeoEye, Scientific Visualization Studio. <https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/205/>

The effect on the Galapagos flora and fauna of these extreme recent ENSOs, including that of 1997/8, was quite variable, reflecting the tolerances and requirements of each species. Some species prospered, especially those dependent on higher temperatures and increased precipitation, including a set of warm-water tropical fish species that arrive, often in large numbers, during ENSOs and can disappear in the intervening years (Grove 1985, Victor et al. 2001). Others suffered major losses, especially those dependent on algal production, such as the marine iguanas (Laurie 1990). More recent studies show that some fishes redistribute (vs. survive) during an ENSO period (e.g. Rastoin-Laplane et al. 2024). Observations indicate that populations of planktivorous fishes that depend on oceanographic primary production for food decreased in numbers during the ENSO (Grove 1985), but population data have not been obtained for these fishes and the various factors and outcomes for each species are unresolved.

Fig. 3. *Azurina eupalama*, engraving of type specimen from Heller & Snodgrass (1903).

The case of the Galapagos Damsel fish

One of the most vulnerable species was the Galapagos Damsel fish, *Azurina eupalama*. They were typically found in heterotypic feeding schools with the abundant Scissortail Chromis, *A. atrilobata* (Grove & Lavenberg 1997). The species was first discovered in 1898 and described in 1903 from 8 specimens collected at Floreana and Espanola (Fig. 3) (Grove & Lavenberg 1997). They are obligate schooling planktivores, found in shallow water along rocky and coral reefs, most frequently adjacent to drop-offs where planktivores concentrate. Furthermore, they are an endemic species, with the entire population associated with the exposed, hard-bottom shorelines of the archipelago. The single putative record from Cocos Island is of uncertain provenance, and has not been repeated (McCosker & Rosenblatt 2010).

Their limited geographic range at the margins of the TEP is characteristic of these damselfishes; the northern sister species, *Azurina hirundo*, is found only on the remote oceanic islands of the Revillagigedo Islands, south of Baja California, and extending northward to a few small offshore islands, at Guadalupe, Cedros, Alijos Rocks, and, recently with the post-ENSO warming ocean, to the Channel Islands off southern California (Lea & McAlary 1994). *Azurina hirundo* also has a limited population size – indeed, the recent 2022 expedition to the species' type location at the Revillagigedo Islands, with a broad photographic and collecting survey at all 4 major islands, by the Universidad Autonoma de Baja California Sur (UABCS), Smithsonian Tropical Research Institute (STRI), Scripps Institution of Oceanography, and Los Angeles County Museum, did not encounter a single *A. hirundo* (but schools have been photographed subsequently, at Socorro, in 2024, see www.inaturalist.org).

Unfortunately, the Galapagos Damsel fish has not been seen since 1983, when it was photographed by the senior author (JSG) at Sullivan Bay, Santiago Island (Fig. 4) (Grove & Lavenberg 1997). In the more than 40 years since, divers and naturalists have been looking for any trace of the species. Notably, the Galapagos is particularly

Fig. 4. *Azurina eupalama*, last documented evidence of its existence, photographed in 1983 by Jack Stein Grove at Sullivan Bay, Santiago Island, Galapagos Archipelago.

diligently explored and dived, by well known expert local residents as well as a series of expeditions by visiting ichthyologists and continuing intensive surveys by scientists from the Galapagos National Park, the Charles Darwin Foundation, and, most recently, the East Pacific Corridor Alliance (EPCA) in their photo-documentation expedition in May 2024. That expedition focused on poorly documented, rare, and potentially new fish species, including searching for Galapagos Damsel fish. Thousands of underwater photographs were obtained, some of species never before photographed and some of species that were new records for the islands. Despite these efforts, no Galapagos Damsel fish were found. In addition, the Galapagos is perhaps the top destination for professional and amateur underwater photographers, with several guidebooks and great numbers of published (and available online) underwater photographs and videos that have been seen by people who would recognize the Galapagos Damsel fish.

Furthermore, all diving trips are accompanied by trained naturalists from the Galapagos National Park, most of whom are excellent fish observers and they frequently encounter and photograph rare and vagrant species, many reported for the first (sometimes only) time and enumerated in the latest listings of the fishes of the Galapagos Archipelago which confirmed a total of 683 species of fishes of 178 families (Grove et al. 2022, Victor et al. 2024).

The senior author JSG authored the seminal guidebook “The Fishes of the Galapagos Islands” (Grove & Lavenberg 1997) and has 5 decades of experience surveying fishes in the archipelago. In that book, the authors note that *A. eupalama* is not common, but widely observed at regular locations at all of the main islands in the archipelago, except for the two northernmost of Wolf and Darwin. JSG has been looking for the Galapagos Damsel fish for about 40 years since, without success, and especially focusing on previously known sites.

Prior to 1983, Galapagos Damsel fish had not been difficult to find and collect. They were repeatedly collected by prior expeditions, with about 40 lots listed at several museums, starting with the discovery of the species on the 1898/1899 Hopkins-Stanford Galapagos Expedition and then described by Edmund Heller and Robert E. Snodgrass (1903). Subsequently, they were collected on almost every major expedition to the Galapagos: by Alexander Agassiz on the *Albatross* in 1904; Rollo Beck on the California Academy of Sciences expedition in 1905; William Beebe on the *Arcturus* Oceanographic Expedition in 1925; Alf Wollebaek on the Norwegian Zoological Expedition in 1925; Smithsonian curator Waldo Schmitt on the Hancock-Pacific Galapagos Expedition on the *Velero III* in 1934; George S. Myers on the Allan Hancock Pacific Expedition, also on the *Velero III*, in 1938; Waldo Schmitt again, on the Franklin D. Roosevelt Presidential Cruise in 1938; Loren P. Woods of the Field Museum in 1941; Henry W. Fowler on the Fifth Vanderbilt Expedition in 1941; the IATTC expedition on the *Mauritania* in 1952; Boyd Walker on the University of California expedition on the *Golden Bear* in 1964; L.W. Knapp on the *Anton Bruun* in 1966; Richard R. Rosenblatt on the Scripps Institution of Oceanography expedition on the *Alpha Helix* in 1967; John McCosker on the California Academy of Science expedition in 1977 at Bartolome; and C.L. Smith on the Scripps Institution of Oceanography expedition on the *Alpha Helix* in 1978. The absence of any specimens collected since 1978 is remarkable.

Extinction of the Galapagos Damsel fish

Grove et al. (2023) reviewed the status of *A. eupalama* for the The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species meeting in Puerto Ayora in September 2022. Their conclusion was that the species was critically endangered, possibly extinct, based entirely on the absence of any evidence of the damselfish for more than 40 years. Declaring the species extinct was not considered since it is essentially proving a negative, especially with the difficulty in establishing absence beyond a reasonable doubt. However, in comparison to other cases of critically endangered marine fishes evaluated by the IUCN, the species is not small and inconspicuous, camouflaged, deep, or hidden, and they occur in schools in clear water at diving depths in one of the most visited dive areas in the world.

Why would *Azurina eupalama* go extinct while other planktivore populations may have been reduced yet persisted through the ENSO? Unlike the other planktivorous fishes in Galapagos, *A. eupalama* is both endemic and apparently adapted to cooler subtropical conditions, since it is not found anywhere in the wide band of tropical habitat on the mainland of Central America and associated offshore islands (Robertson & Allen 2024). Correspondingly, the northern sister species, *Azurina hirundo*, is limited to the subtropical and temperate waters off Colima and Baja California in Mexico and California (Robertson & Allen 2024). In contrast, wide-ranging

tropical fish planktivores, including *Azurina* (ex-*Chromis*) *atrilobata*, would be most adapted to warm tropical waters where the majority of their populations occur. Furthermore, *A. eupalama* were always found associated with schools of *A. atrilobata*, who were both ubiquitous and typically in greater numbers, and thus competition due to the overlap in prey would undoubtedly be an additional stressor on the endemic species.

Is this the first documented modern extinction of a marine fish?

Extinction of marine shorefishes, especially tropical marine bony fishes, is mostly prevented by the pelagic dispersal of larvae. Almost all tropical marine fishes, other than the chondrichthyans, have a larval phase that spends some time in the plankton, dispersing to varying degrees offshore before returning to settle or associate with the shoreline. There are a very few notable exceptions, and those have restricted distributions, typically limited to continental margins. The patchy distribution of suitable habitat in tropical marine regions, either as segments of shorelines or, over much of the tropics, a patchy distribution of islands and archipelagos of various sizes, has no doubt promoted the evolution of a dispersal phase to avoid progressive local extirpations. The dispersal stage makes an extinction much less likely since there is always the probability of recolonization of areas where populations are disappearing.

Features that would promote extinction are commercial exploitation, restricted distributions, especially island endemism, short dispersal phases (or none in elasmobranchs and a few bony shorefishes), relatively low fecundity, low population sizes, small size, short lifespan, group or schooling behaviors (especially for spawning), along with narrow adaptive niches, limited tolerances, vulnerability to predation and competition, and occupying physically variable or marginal locations. Several of these features make the Galapagos Damsel fish especially vulnerable.

There are very few putative cases of a marine fish extinction. Several are postulated from the presence of historically unique type specimens of named species that were never found again. An example is the Java Stingaree (Stingray), *Urolophus javanicus*, known from a single specimen from a fish market described by Martens in 1864 and not seen in the subsequent 160 years (Constance et al. 2023). Those cases need to have their taxonomy critically evaluated, and would be unresolved and certainly are not a documented extinction of a known population.

Another putative case, in this case in temperate waters, is the apparent disappearance of the Smooth Handfish, *Sympterichthys unipennis*, off south-eastern Australia, where it has been considered likely extinct (Last et al. 2020). The species that has not been recorded in any surveys since 2000. Notably, these fishes do not have a pelagic larval phase, and reside in areas that are trawled, making them vulnerable to extirpation (note that several critically endangered handfishes, i.e. Pink, Red, and Narrowbody, around southeast Australia, have been rediscovered in the wild after apparent disappearances). Very recently, in 2025, the IUCN Species Survival Commission's Standards and Petitions Committee ruled that the listing of the Smooth Handfish should be changed from extinct to data deficient, pending additional assessment (<https://www.iucnredlist.org/species/123423283/207621852>).

The potential of eDNA for the search

What would it take to declare the Galapagos Damsel fish officially extinct? The utility of DNA sequencing for the identification of fish species in the marine environment has advanced rapidly in the past decade, and the "barcoding" technique has been widely used to identify fish species (Ratnasingham & Hebert 2007, Ward et al. 2009, Victor et al. 2015). Victor (2024) successfully identified 66 species of larval fishes in oceanic waters around the Galapagos EEZ using this technique. DNA barcoding is using a standard mitochondrial gene sequence to identify species by matching to voucher sequences, in the case of the Barcode of Life project, BOLD (www.boldsystems.org), the gene for cytochrome c oxidase or COI.

In its most impressive new application, environmental DNA (eDNA), the innumerable fragments of DNA present in ambient water samples can be amplified and the short sequences obtained used to match to database sequences and thus assemble a list of the species present in the area (Ruppert, Kline & Rahman 2019). The technique has proven to be effective in detecting hundreds of fish species from water samples in a variety of locations (e.g. Dukan et al. 2024), although not yet applied to the Galapagos marine fauna. One limitation of the

technique is that it requires a comprehensive reference library of confirmed and validated species sequences to match to, and, at present, the matches are often not close enough to determine species in a sea of close relatives. Exacerbating the problem is that unidentified or misidentified sequences are common in the disparate databases, which typically have little to no taxonomic quality control. In the case of the Galapagos fish fauna, we have developed a reference library for most of the shorefish species, and most of the remaining taxa can be matched to sister species from nearby regions. This initiative is a critical prerequisite for any reliable detection of eDNA to potentially confirm the persistence of *A. eupalama* in the Galapagos Islands.

The relevance of eDNA to the question of the status of the Galapagos Damselfish is that it should provide an additional, and notably independent, evidence of absence, with the caveats that eDNA surveys are not direct reflections of the local species assemblage, but can be selective in unanticipated ways. However, it is one more method to help confirm there is no sign of the species since the 1982/3 ENSO. Ongoing efforts employing this technique in the search for this species have opportunistically sampled both coastal and pelagic ecosystems across the Galapagos Archipelago (A. Hearn and D. Pazmiño, pers. comm.). However, targeted expeditions to historical sites associated with *A. eupalama* are essential for a rigorous eDNA sampling protocol.

An expedition is planned for May 2025, for a team of experts to visit those sites where the Galapagos Damselfish was commonly found prior to the 1982/3 ENSO. By carrying out intensive reef surveys at these sites and collecting water samples at multiple depths for eDNA analysis, this would be the most comprehensive search for the species to date. The findings should establish, if not beyond, at least inching past, a reasonable doubt whether the species persists unnoticed at one or more locations, or whether it followed Lonesome George, the iconic last giant tortoise from the Pinta Island species, into extinction.

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